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TITLE: Comprehensive circuit model of auto-limiting superconductor devices and systems

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Abstract Body : The use of superconducting (HTS) auto limiting structures has been proven over the past few years through the realization of simple limiting superconductor transmission lines and resonators, by exploiting the transition phenomena from superconductor to normal state. This achievement opens the possibility of using superconductors for the design of complex, frequency selective and functional auto-limiting architectures. Application of those are several, which go from RADAR protection of jamming signals to the coexistence between very different RF/microwave systems, such as cellular communication with high power radars. When this happens, it is crucial that they can operate without detrimental of mutual interferences and damaging. These challenges demand for continuous research on novel multifunctional devices.

To give response this major challenge, this work presents a comprehensive circuit model that accounts for all the dynamic phenomena occurring on the transition from superconducting state to normal state of the HTS section that is responsible of the auto-limiting function. The circuit model evaluates the current density distribution along the limiting section and applies fundamental equations to recalculate the new conductivity due to its inherent nonlinear dependence. The new conductivity is then used to evaluate the dissipated power and its corresponding heating occurring in the section. Heat flow through the substrate and temperature dependence of the involved parameters are also considered in the model. The new conditions on temperature and current density distribution are then used again to model the propagation effect. This process repeats as an iterative procedure according the signal travelling along the circuit.

This circuit model is then used to design and evaluate the application of the auto-limiting concept to more complex structures such as RF filters and multiplexers. Comparison between two useful multiplexing architectures will be assessed. The first structure will consist on a multiplexing structure based on channeling filters and isolators, whereas the second architecture will use 90 degree branch line couplers instead of isolators.

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